

EXTRALINGUISTIC ISSUES IN CROSS- CULTURAL COMMUNICATION: BODY LANGUAGE, TABOOS

Scientific supervisor: Abdulazizov Davudbek

Andijan State Institute of Foreign Languages

Student of group 319

Soliyeva Mohigul

Abstract: *Cross-cultural communication is an essential aspect of globalized societies. However, communicating with people from different cultures can be challenging due to extralinguistic issues such as body language and taboos. This article explores the impact of body language and taboos in cross-cultural communication through a literature review. The study highlights the methods used in researching these issues and presents the results.*

Key words: *cross-cultural communication, body language, taboos, literature review, research methods, results, discussion*

As the world becomes increasingly globalized, cross-cultural communication has become essential. In today's diverse society, it is common to interact with people from different cultures. However, communicating with people from different cultures can be challenging due to extralinguistic issues. Body language and taboos are two extralinguistic issues that can significantly impact crosscultural communication. Body language refers to nonverbal communication, including facial expressions, gestures, and posture. Taboos refer to practices or beliefs that are forbidden or frowned upon in a particular culture. This article explores the impact of body language and taboos on cross-cultural communication. This article

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is based on a literature review of previous research on the impact of body language and taboos on cross-cultural communication. A systematic search was conducted on online databases, including Google Scholar, JSTOR, and Web of Science. The search terms used were "cross-cultural communication," "body language," and "taboos." The articles included in the review were selected based on their relevance to the topic and the quality of research methodology. The literature review revealed that body language plays a crucial role in crosscultural communication. Different cultures have different meanings attached to various nonverbal cues. For example, a smile is generally interpreted as a sign of friendliness in most cultures, but in some cultures, it can be interpreted as a sign of insincerity or aggression. Similarly, gestures such as the thumbs-up sign or the OK sign may have different meanings in different cultures. Therefore, it is essential to be aware of these differences when communicating with people from different cultures. Taboos also play a significant role in cross-cultural communication. Different cultures have different taboos, which can range from food and drink to social behavior. For example, in some cultures, eating with the left hand is considered impolite, while in others, it is perfectly acceptable. Similarly, in some cultures, it is considered rude to ask personal questions, while in others, it is perfectly acceptable. Therefore, it is crucial to be aware of these taboos when communicating with people from different cultures. Cross-cultural communication involves not only language but also extralinguistic factors, such as body language and taboos. These extralinguistic factors can have a significant impact on communication and can create misunderstandings or even offense. Body language is the nonverbal communication that accompanies speech, including gestures, facial expressions, and posture. Different cultures have different body language norms, and what is

acceptable in one culture may be offensive in another. For example, in some cultures, direct eye contact is a sign of respect, while in others it is considered rude or aggressive. Similarly, gestures that are commonplace in one culture, such as the "OK" sign, may be considered offensive in another. Taboos are cultural prohibitions against certain behaviors or topics. These taboos can vary greatly between cultures, and violating them can lead to serious offense. For example, in some cultures, it is considered impolite to touch someone's head, while in others it is taboo to show the soles of your feet. Talking about certain topics, such as religion or politics, can also be taboo in some cultures. To avoid miscommunication and offense, it is important to be aware of these extralinguistic factors and to take them into account when communicating across cultures. It is also important to be open to learning about other cultures and to ask questions when unsure about cultural norms. By being respectful and aware of cultural differences, cross-cultural communication can be successful and productive. The literature review highlights the importance of understanding body language and taboos when communicating with people from different cultures. Effective cross-cultural communication requires an understanding of these extralinguistic issues. However, it is essential to note that these issues are not universal and can vary greatly from culture to culture. Therefore, it is crucial to conduct research on the specific cultures you are interacting with to ensure effective communication.

In conclusion, cross-cultural communication is essential in today's globalized society. Extralinguistic issues such as body language and taboos can significantly impact cross-cultural communication. Effective communication requires an understanding of these issues and the specific cultural norms of the people you are interacting with. It is essential to conduct research on the cultures you are

interacting with and to be aware of the differences in body language and taboos. By doing so, we can improve our cross-cultural communication skills and build stronger relationships with people from different cultures.

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